

An Efficient Deep Learning Approach for Patient Monitoring using Optimized fruit fly Algorithm in Wireless Body Sensor Network

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Abstract

Health maintenance systems are specialized monitoring systems that keep track of the core activities of life. The goal of the project was to design and build wireless body sensor networks for monitoring key functions in real time. In emergency situations, WBSNs must process vast amounts of data in order to make feasible decisions. As a result, this research addresses these issues by presenting a Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA) as a deep learning framework for assessing health effects. The WBSN nodes are initially used to gather data from patient medical records in order to obtain specific metrics for the evaluation. Based on the acquired metrics, WBSN nodes send information to the destination node. The Fruit Fly Algorithm is used to find the best cluster head in this case. The findings of the hybrid Fruit fly Algorithm are then passed on to the target node, where the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is utilized to categorize the health information for risk evaluation. The suggested SMA is used to train the CNN in this case. The proposed SMA performs better on measures such as accuracy, energy, and throughput, with values of 94.604%, 0.145, and 0.058, respectively.

Keywords: Health Monitoring, Wireless Body Sensor Network (WBSN), Fruit fly (FF) optimization algorithm, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA).

1.INTRODUCTION:

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) include WBSNs, that are used in healthcare systems to observe patients' medical conditions [1]. A wireless sensor network in human health monitoring allows patients to recognize his/her physical health on a real - time basis and respond quickly to emergencies.[2]. WSNs are commonly used to obtain data from the environment because of their minimum energy consumption, low price, and huge implementation.[3]. WBSN users can also use the Internet to access body sensor data and resources from anywhere in the world. WSNs were also multi-hop self-organizing connectivity systems consisting of wireless sensor nodes placed throughout the sensing area.[4]. The wearable WSNs' key advantages are their compact size, light weight, and portability [5]. WSNs, also

referred as motes, are small computers able to perform light processing, sensing, and wireless communication with other wsns in a sensor network system. In a single compact container, the motes combine computing, sensing, and wireless networking. A wireless sensor node must have a radio interface including an antenna for wireless transmission, as well as a CPU, memory, analogue or biochemical detectors (e.g., ECG, temperature, glucose), and a battery for electricity [6]. As the number of sensor nodes in wireless sensor networks rises, so does the energy consumption, network transmission delay, poor transmission quality due to data transmission congestion, data transmission being halted due to partial node failure, and other issues [3]. Due to the low price of sensor nodes, node/link failure is common in wireless sensor networks, and data loss/abnormality is a common occurrence [7]. WBAN stands for Wireless Body Area Network and is a type of WSN [1]. It has become possible to connect low-power, lightweight, and small physiological sensors to establish a Body Area Network (BAN). The WBAN is established when this connection is augmented by wireless technology. The natural union of connection and miniaturization is represented by this network. WBAN is made up of a variety of sensors. Heart rate, blood pressure, and blood oxygen saturation are some of the vital signs gathered, processed, and transferred by these sensors [8]. WBANs are wireless communication networks which focus just on the human body and include a local processing unit (LPU), individual connectors, network equipment, and detectors placed on or in the body. The sensors' data is wirelessly transferred to the Logical Processing Unit (LPU) for real-time disease analysis and diagnosis. These data can also be sent to other servers for additional processing [9]. A doctor in a distant location could quickly examine the data and make a treatment recommendation [2]. WSNs (wireless sensor networks) and WBANs (wireless body area networks) are very similar [9].

The fruit fly optimization technique is depends upon the fruit fly's foraging behaviour., is a new popular way for accomplishing universal optimization [10]. The (FOA)Fruit Fly Optimization Algorithm is utilised as a cluster head selection after parameter identification. Slime Mold Algorithm (SMA) is a new meta-heuristic optimization method developed by A. Heidari and inspired by the natural oscillation mode of slime moulds. SMA is an optimization strategy that is applied after the fruit fly optimization algorithm but before the classifier is applied [11]. Due to its superior feature extraction capabilities, deep learning is widely utilised in recognition of images and NLP, medical diagnosis and treatment, infrastructure engineering, and other domains. CNN is a well-known deep learning algorithm [12]. A feedforward neural network (CNN) is a type of neural network with convolutional computations that can handle a variety of information formats with audio or visual information, for example, have translation invariance [3]. CNN is a popular neural network model for modulation categorization. The input signal dimensions assisted by CNN in CNN-based modulation evaluation metrics is usually fixed in most cases. On the other hand, the period of the exact radio wave flare is unknown. When the radio wave length exceeds the CNN input length, it becomes a problem to figure out how to use the entire radio wave flare to improve accuracy of classification [13]. A CNN (multilayer neural network) is a deep learning model made up of one or more CNN layers and one or more fully connected layers [14]. The convolutional neural network (CNN), is the most well known deep learning models, can extract a wide variety of data by utilizing different filtration with in convolutional layers, pooling layers, normalization layers, and fully connected layers, resulting in improved task completion behavior [15]. The classifier will be the final step in generating our output. The main concern of their well-wishers is to keep track of their health, which can be done efficiently with the help of BSN [16].

The proposed SMA-based CNN classifier is used in this paper to analyze patient health information for the purpose of determining health risks [1]. The WBSN nodes first scan the patient's information from health records such as the patient's identification number, his or her age in years, gender, as well as the location of the pain in the chest, among other things. The WBSN nodes transfer the perceived information to the destination node after sensing the appropriate parameters. In this case, the FOA is used to choose the best grouping heads in the WBSN model.

The proposed SMA-based CNN classifier that uses the presented SMA for CNN and the Fruitfly method for cluster head selection, is the research's main contribution [1].

The paper is organized in the following way: Section 1 contains an introductory section based on WBAN-based hazard assessment, and Section 2 includes an article analysis of the already established techniques of evaluation of health hazards with obstacles. The modelling approach for tracking health problems via WBAN is shown in Section 3, and the performance of the system for tracking health issues is described in Part 4. The overview is provided in part 5. Part 6 explains the findings as well as the recommended approach, and Part 7 wraps up the paper [1].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Alameen, A., & Gupta, A. (2020) developed Optimization Driven Deep Learning Approach for Health Monitoring and Risk Assessment in Wireless Body Sensor Networks. Wireless body sensor networks (WBSNs) are affordable alternative that can be used with a variety of clinical applications and play an important part in monitoring patient health status. WBSNs face significant hurdles in processing enormous amounts of information and making practical assessments in critical situations. The ideal cluster head is determined using a Particle Swarm Optimization and a hybrid Harmony Search Algorithm (hybrid HSA-PSO). The Scalp Swarm Algorithm based on Fractional Cat Swarm Optimization (FCSSA) is proposed in this paper for training the DBN classifier for analyzing health hazards. The outputs of the hybrid HSA-PSO are then delivered to the target node, which classifies the patient records for emergency assessment using the Deep Belief Network (DBN) [1].

A deep learning technique is applied to extract features of various attributes from pre-processed data in this study. To obtain abstract features from pre-processed sensory input, Cheng.H et al. (2019) presented 1-D CNN (One Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network) and Bi-LSTM artificial neural networks (Bidirectional Long and Short-Term Memory). The one-step prediction is then obtained using these abstract features. Finally, they introduced multi-step prediction, which involves repeatedly using past historical data and prediction findings. The suggested model outperforms earlier methods in predicting multi-step sensory input, according to the results [3].

Wireless Body Area Networks with Cellular-aided Device-to-Device Communications for patient Monitoring was developed by P.-Y. Kong et al. (2020). (WBAN). For healthcare monitoring, each person who uses a wireless body area network (WBAN). This WBAN may collide, resulting in a severe reduction in communication quality of service and latency for healthcare applications. To avoid a collision, the body sensor is connected to a hub within the WBAN using cellular assisted device-device-to-device (D2D) communication. To manage transmit power and assign communication channels, this abstract employs a combination of several optimization techniques as well as the Hungarian algorithm. Finally, the outcome indicates that WBAN collisions can be avoided [17].

The most important challenge in researching the mobile wireless sensor networks is network optimization (MWSN). In recent years, researchers have suggested a number of unique swarm intelligence optimization algorithms that have shown promising experimental results when compared to classic swarm intelligence algorithms that have flaws or failures when tackling difficult multi-objective optimization algorithms. These swarm intelligence algorithms are commonly employed in presentation improvement. Cluster intelligence improves the performance of wireless sensor networks. This research by L.Cao et al. (2019) focuses on analyzing and summarizing Swarm intelligence algorithmic technologies and significant mobile wireless sensor network technologies. The issues and responses are summarized, and the concerns that need to be addressed, as well as the future prospects for this research direction and development trend, are anticipated in connection with the existing research state [4]

Vibration-Based Structural Health Monitoring Using Deep Learning was proposed by G. Toh and J. Park in 2020. Vibration-based structural health monitoring is being done with deep learning technologies. These vibrations are

utilized to extract features in order to diagnose the system. Due to their flexibility and resilience, deep-learning-based techniques are also used in this paper to find growing application in difficulties. Deep learning is effective in structural health monitoring and as a technique for solving vibration concerns. Algorithms for machine learning are employed for fault monitoring and structural integrity monitoring based on vibrations, according to the findings of this study [18].

In this research, Liao, Y., et al. (2020) developed a method based on deep learning in order to automate of the physical rehabilitation exercises' quality. The framework's key components include functions for scoring for translating performance indicators into numerical movement quality scores, metrics for assessing movement performance, and deep neural network models for producing input movement quality rating through supervised learning. The suggested performance metric encapsulates low-dimensional data representation achieved using a deep autoencoder network and is based on the log-likelihood of a Gaussian mixture model., according to the researchers. It also uses subsystems for calculating joint displacements of different components of the body, which takes use of the spatial peculiarities of human movements. This research is significant since it is the initial to use neural networks with deep learning to measure performance in rehabilitation [19].

To divide health-monitoring equipment into clusters. the suggested approach uses a centralized cluster-based hierarchical routing system. Yang, G. (2020) developed a centralized hierarchical clustering strategy in a smart healthcare system for green communication, which explains how to monitor patients in a cost-effective manner using a hierarchical approach based on clusters (green communication).Sensor-embedded devices keep an eye on things numerous vital indicators of number of patients in smart healthcare systems, and the gadgets run on small batteries, so energy is used efficiently. By decreasing the duty-cycling of equipment, a heuristic method is used in smart healthcare techniques for conservation of energy. The obstacles encountered when conducting an experiment were data gathering, scheduling, and transmission to the base station are all part of the process. The cluster head is employed to collect these states in this case. To address these issues, a hierarchical clustering strategy for energy-efficient patient monitoring has been developed. As a result of this technique, the network lifetime is increased while energy consumption is lowered during various states, and the data quality in making decisions based on the patient's vital indicators [20].

K.Zhang and W.Ling (2020) proposed a wireless telemedicine health monitoring device with many physical parameters that investigates the system's structure and functionality in general needs. Temperature, oxygen saturation in the blood, respiration, ECG, pulse and blood pressure are examples of human physiological parameters. Fabric electrodes, a discrete Fourier transform method, and a reflection type photoelectric sensor are utilized in this research to extract human biosignals, breathing signals, and realize human pulse signal reflection, respectively. The threshold algorithm for self-learning as per the plethysmography signals and continuous cuff-free measurement, BP is paired with ECG. They tested the total system's operation to ensure the fact that the data collected from physiology of humans signal is correct, as well as its validity and dependability [21].

A practical study of a deep learning-based IDS called the Clustered Restricted Boltzmann Machine-Intrusion Detection System (RBC-IDS). A thorough examination in the application of machine learning and deep learning (DL) technologies in wireless sensor networks for intrusion detection systems (IDS) (WSNs). S. Otoum (2019), have made a detection using Deep Learning in Intrusion Detection by Sensor Networks, developed this IDS. RBC-IDS stands for RBC Identification System.is performed particularly when compared to IDS based on adaptive machine learning and clustered hybrid IDS previously proposed by the author (ASCH-IDS). The RBC-IDS has been developed through simulations compared against the ASCH-IDS with various number of layers hidden. The results reveal that RBC-IDS and ASCH-IDS are the same thing that the obtain rates of detection and accuracy that are roughly double that of ASCH-IDS over time [22].

O.Salem et al. (2021) offer a detection of change points model for centralized detection of anomalies that is based on the Markov chain and is generated from the RMSE between (Root Mean Square Error) and (Root Mean Square Error) anticipated given the values that have been measured for full features. The monitored is transformed by RMSE properties and divides them into overlapping sliding windows. When a successful change is made in k successive number of deviating attributes in windows is utilized in order to distinguish incorrect measures taken during a medical emergency. They tested this method using real-world data from the Physionet database and compared it to other methods. It has a low false alarm rate and a good detection accuracy [23].

SHM Application in Wireless Sensor Networks: Energy Optimization with Higher Information Quality was created by M. C.G. Judith., and V. Geetha (2019). The term "energy" refers to the amount of valuable resources that are depleted in Sensor nodes that are wireless. For applications such as monitoring the structural health (SHM) and monitoring by the military, a low-energy routing protocol for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) has been developed. The clustering technique is used to optimize energy in this paper. The positioning of sensor nodes is optimized significant applications for SHM because it is a cost-effective strategy if the requisite the standard of information is attained with fewer node sensors. The sensor node position optimization is done using an exhaustive search strategy. For effective routing, with an energy-efficient node the highest remaining vitality and the closest connected to the sink node is chosen as the cluster's header from the selected sensor nodes. As a result, nodes that have run out of energy execute nothing but energy harvesting and transmitting their available data to the sink. To maximize nodes, routing efficiency sends their data to the shortest path to the sink node route. Finally, when it comes to information quality with a small total number of nodes and each node has a high residual energy [7].

3. SYSTEM MODEL

The WBSN system architecture for monitoring healthcare applications is detailed in this part, as shown in Figure 1. Human body, WBSN sensor, sink node, laptop or mobile phone, and medical database make up this system model.

Figure 1. System model for WBSN**4. Proposed Assessment Model for Health Risk Using Proposed SMA Based CNN****4.1 Overview**

The system is based on a wireless sensor network and the project's goal is to design and build wireless body sensor networks for real-time monitoring of key functions. By obtaining the parameters, data is transmitted from the WSN nodes in the target node, this is where the fruit fly algorithm is used to create the best cluster head selection. Before using classifiers, the SMA algorithm is implemented for better performance. Finally, the CNN is used to classify health records in order to determine health risks. The proposed dataset has been validated using accuracy, energy, throughput. The block diagram of the proposed methodology is shown below at figure 2.

Figure 2. Block diagram of health assessment using proposed FF-SMA based CNN**4.2 Optimal Cluster Head Selection Using fruitfly algorithm**

Initially Optimal Cluster Head Selection Using Fruitfly Algorithm is implemented to process the data.

FF is an optimization of swarm technique based on the behaviour of fruit foragers flies who use their visual and smell functions to find food. FF is a fictional character mostly accustomed to choose the shortest distance between cluster nodes and CHs. It calculates the reciprocal of the separation between neighbouring CHs after measuring the distance between them. Following that, it compares each and every measurable value and selects the lowest. The Algorithm FF adds up the values along a specific distance before applying the two primary functions of fruit flies. The vision function does not select the maximum distance; it just selects the minimum distance. The following is a breakdown of the Fruit Fly algorithm:

- Set the algorithm variables to their default values.
- Defining the Variables in the Algorithm.
- Calculate the distance as well as the concentration value.
- Determining the fitness function.
- Calculate the maximum concentration.
- Maintaining the highest concentration level possible.
- Checking and re-checking.

These are the steps to be taken in the following seven subcategories:

Step 1: The cluster's beginning position is random and in (0,0) coordinates, as shown in

Init Xar = 0; Init Yar = 0

Step 2: Managing the movement of the search for the distance between every CH individual's neighbours.

$$X_i = X_{ar} + \text{Rand Val}$$

$$Y_i = Y_{ar} + \text{Rand Val}$$

Step 3: Once the site of the event neighbouring CHs is established, the distance (D) between the neighbouring CHs. Nodes in the CH classification are determined prior to making a decision on the concentration of odour (S), which is the reciprocal distance, is calculated.

$$D_i = \sqrt{(X_i^2 + Y_i^2)}$$

$$S_i = 1 / D_i$$

Step 4: To figure out what the fragrance is like at the position of the fruit fly, the concentration of odour value is taken. In the smell concentration or fitness functions, it has been substituted.

$$\text{Smelli} = \text{Func}(S_i)$$

Step 5: Calculate the distance between the pathways with the least number of nodes and the highest concentration of odours.

$$[\text{bSmellpNode}] = \min(\text{node})$$

$$[\text{bSmellbNode}] = \max(\text{smell})$$

Step 6: Maintain the highest odour value possible have the node send the information acquired over the network that utilizes the fitness values.

$$\text{Smellb} = \text{bNode}$$

Step 7: This is where iterative optimization takes in with the sensor nodes in a controlled manner for each node position.

4.3 Clustering with the FF Algorithm:

The FF is a fictional character method is a clustering technique that optimizes. Assume you're working within a framework of N nodes of sensors grouped in P clusters: C1, C2, ..., Cp, where the nodes are fixed and BS is fixed are separated into multiple clusters based on energy and location data of each node. The information transmission procedure is broken into a circle. The CHs gather data from each and every member of the group and communicate it as per the BS at the end of each round. The job is accomplished in two stages: the first is a model of clustering, and the second is transfer of data.

A. Clustering Model Process:

In this case of the clustering system, every sensor node broadcasts information to the BS, including their physical state and level of energy. When this data is fed into the BS, it will calculate the usual level of energy that is always changing. Only nodes with leftover energy above the typical level are eligible to be an instant CH stands for a circle or a running round. In order to enhance the detection of CHs, the FF Algorithm is employed to find heads of ideal p cluster, with the goal perform in being used to determine the at the very least, shown below:

$$f_1 = \max_p \left\{ \sum_{\forall i \in cp} d(n_i, CH_p) / |C_p| \right\}$$

$$f_2 = \sum_{i=1}^N E(n_i) / \sum_{p=1}^K E(CH_p)$$

$$f(x) = \alpha \times f_1 + (1 - \alpha) \times f_2$$

f_1 is the cost function in this case, representing the most extreme point in the Euclidean space between nodes. iVi cluster C_p , and their heads in a clusters CH_p , and $|C_p|$ represents the number of nodes that can be accommodated in a cluster C_p . f_2 , on the other hand, is the ratio of the initial energy of this network frame's active node, $E(\text{node}_i)$, to the running round, the aggregate existing drive of the running cluster head, $E(CH_p)$. The constant displays f_1 and f_2 's commitment to the goal f . capacity (x). This goal has a function propensity to degrade the average intra-cluster distance between the cluster head and the sensor nodes while also improving the energy efficiency of the network topology. Head nodes that aren't in a cluster transfer information to the BS as it travels through the cluster heads, once the cluster has been constructed. Each information cycle exchange is related with sensor nodes, the technique for picking clusters is reshaped. During transmission between nodes to the CH, the remaining power of each node is added to this data and has been added to the information package aids the BS in selecting the cluster head and clusters that are most suited for the next round. The CH creates a schedule in consideration of taking into account the amount of dynamic nodes, Time Division Multiple Access is used within the tangle (TDMA).

B. Transmission of Data

The CHs are a type initially configured. After transmission of information, procedure is established, every sensor's nodes begin transmitting data to the CHs. The data from head nodes that aren't part of a cluster is sent to the CH. The CH collects all of the information from a group and forward it to the BS. Once you've completed one cycle, you'll be ready to go on to the next in a brand-new CH. The whole data transmission process of creating a CH follows a cycle and is picked according to the most powerful node. Furthermore, the TDMA stands for Time Division Multiple Access method is employed; head nodes that aren't part of a cluster which change their node of transmission in the middle of the operation and kill when the transmission is completed. The CHs arrange information collection and accumulation; as a result, the amount a set of data is reduced, and the CHs simply take the lead focused the BS with information.

C. CH Selection Using the FF Algorithm in a Flow Chart:

The diagram of a flowchart for collection of cluster heads in a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is explained in figure 2. [10]

Figure 3. Flow diagram of Fruit Fly Algorithm for Cluster Head Selection

4.4 Proposed SMA Based CNN for the Classification of Health Records

SMA has been used to optimise the data once it has been processed from the cluster head (Algorithm for Slime Moulds).

To optimise hyper parameters, the proposed model employs a Algorithm for slime mould (SMA), which has already been proposed due to the characteristics of a slime mould's oscillation style. The mathematical model contained in the SMA is used to reestablish the comments, both positive and negative of slime fungus proliferation. Multiple

optimization problems, including engineering challenges, could be consolidated using the SMA. The approaching food and warp food stages of the SMA algorithm are the two key phases.

i) Approaching food:

This is the phase where the slime is proceeding toward food depending on its odour present in the air. This process is mathematically defined as follows.

$$X(t + 1) = \{\vec{x}_b(t) + \vec{v}_b \times (W \times \vec{X}_A(t) - \vec{X}_B(t)), r < p \vec{v}_c \times \vec{X}(t), r \geq p\}$$

$\vec{v}_b$ is a specification ranging from -a to a

$\vec{v}_c$ portrays a specification that reduces from one to zero in a linear manner.

X_b constitutes the present single location with respect to high concentration of odour.

t shows the present iteration.

X showcases the slime moulds locality.

X_A and X_B are arbitrarily picked singulars from the mould.

W denotes the mass of the slime mould.

The equation for p could be written as:

$$p = \tanh[S(i) - DF] \text{ Where } i \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$$

S(i) showcases the fitness of $\vec{X}$

As described already, varies from -a to a, which a could be written as:

$$a = \left(\left(-\frac{t}{maxt} \right) + 1 \right)$$

The $\vec{W}$ equation is written as:

$$\underline{W(SmeelIndex(t))} = \{1 + r \times \log \log \left(\frac{bF - S(i)}{bF - wF} + 1 \right), \text{ condition } 1 - r \times \log \left(\frac{bF - S(i)}{bF - wF} + 1 \right), \text{ others}\}$$

$$SmeelIndex = \text{sort}(S)$$

Where, r represents the arbitrary value from the interval [0, 1].

bF showcases the maximum level of performance from the present process of iteration.

wF showcases minimum fitness value acquired from the present process of iteration.

Smeel Index mentions the series of fitness values.

ii) Warp food:

This phase shows the performance of the slime in executing contraction of its venous structure and it is mathematically written as: [27]

$$\vec{X}^* = \{rand \times (UB - LB) + LB.rand < z \vec{X}(t) + vb \times (\vec{W} \times \vec{X}_A(t) - \vec{X}_B(t)), r < p \vec{vc} \times \vec{X}(t), r \geq p$$

D. Architecture of CNN Classifier

The data has been classified using the CNN classifier after it has been processed and optimized using the Fruit Fly Algorithm and Slime Mould Algorithm, respectively. CNN is a feed-forward network that broadcasts content from other sources with a layer for feature extraction. Fully-connected, softmax activation function, and input, convolutional and pooling for feature extraction and classification are the five layers that make up the overall structure. One or more filters (kernels) are applied to input frames in the convolutional layer, which slide in each direction with set steps and produce multiple convolution techniques that are used to create local features. The activation function of the ReLU is applied to features that were extracted to ensure nonlinearity. The layer of pooling receives these and reduces the dimension of space. The features that were extracted are input into one or more fully linked layers, each of which consists of one or more layers. Using the softmax activation function and classification layer, the final fully linked layer allows output to be directed into a class label [5].

CNN is a form of supervised learning. It is made up of numerous convolutional layers that are alternated with pooling layers before fully connected layers are added. The four basic layers of a CNN are as follows:

- **Input layer:** This layer receives the input data and maintains the values.
- **Convolutional layer:** The CNN's main structural layer is the convolutional layer. In this layer, they are convolved with convolution kernels (filters) that slide across the input data, and the stride controls how much the data is convolved by the kernels. The feature map is the name given to the resulting product. This technique not only decreases the input data's dimension, but also pulls relevant information from it automatically.
- **Pooling layer:** Another key structural layer of CNN is the pooling layer, often known as the subsampling layer. It mostly consists of maximum and as well as average pooling. The goal of data input travelling is to go through this stratum lower a large number of parameters and a small number of parameters network's computing while it costs maintaining critical features. Furthermore, the framework efficiently addresses the issue of over-fitting.
- **Layer that is entirely connected:** This layer is fully connected is the same as the classic MLP. This layer can classify the final features that result from the processing of many layers of convolutional and pooling [12].

The CNN architecture is made up of a series of separate layers that use a differentiable function is used to forward the input volume into an output volume (e.g., holding the class scores) shown in figure 3. There are a few different sorts of layers commonly used.

Figure 4. Architecture of CNN classifier

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Configuration for Experiment

The presented framework is put into action in MATLAB as well as runs on a Personal Computer or laptop using Windows 10 operating system.

B. Measurements of Effectiveness

The measurements used in accuracy, energy, and throughput are all factors considered in the analysis, which have been written in the following:

i. Accuracy

Accuracy is determined as: $\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / (\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN})$

where true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative are represented by TP, TN, FP, and FN, respectively.

ii. Energy

The data transferred from the nodes to the cluster heads consumes a significant amount of energy, which can be determined using the following equation:

$$h_2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^Q E(N_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^m E(N_r^C)}$$

where $E(N_i)$ denotes the i^{th} node's initial energy and $E(N^C_x)$ refers to the energy at the x^{th} CH.

iii. Throughput

The throughput is the cumulative number of information packets obtained at a given period:

P is the sum of information packets obtained at simulation time r, hence throughput = P / r .

C. Representation of the set of data

The experiment is conducted utilizing the Disease of the Heart Data Set from the UCI machine learning repository (<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/heart+Disease>) by combining two databases, Cleveland and Switzerland, and the dataset's donor is David W. Aha. There are 303 instances, 76 characteristics, and 818838 hits in the dataset. The goal is to determine whether the patient has cardiac disease, which can be determined by using values (1, 2, 3, or 4) to represent presence and 0 to represent absence.

D. Comparing Methods

The HSA-PSO + FCSSA approach was utilised to make the comparison, which was then compared to the suggested FRUIT FLY + SMA method.

E. Comparative Analysis

Using the databases from Cleveland and Switzerland with nodes of 50 and 100, this section examines the comparative methodologies when it comes to performance metrics like energy efficiency, throughput, and accuracy.

i. Using the Cleveland database for analysis:

For a total node of 50: In terms of precision, energy, and output, a comparison of the existing HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the proposed fruitfly+SMA-CNN for 50 nodes is shown. Initially, existing HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested fruitfly+SMA-CNN accuracy values are 88.353 % and 90.252 %, respectively. The values of accuracy assessed by the already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested fruitfly+SMA-CNN after the process are 93.323 % and 94.206 %, respectively. The values of energy are measured by the already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested FF+SMA-CNN when the number of rounds is 0 are 0.548 and 0.55, respectively. Existing HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested fruitfly+SMA compute energy values of 0.0737 and 0.1208 for 2000 rounds, respectively. The study according to accuracy, energy and throughput parameters is shown in Figure 5 (a) (b) and (c) respectively. The approach achieves maximum energy parameters of 1J when the number of iterations is zero and then reduces the number of rounds. The throughput values are determined by already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested fruitfly+SMA when the number of rounds is 2000 are 0.057 and 0.060, respectively. As a result, it can be concluded that the suggested fruitfly+SMA method outperforms previous protocols.

Using 100 nodes: The existing HAS-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the proposed Fruitfly+SMA+CNN have accuracy values of 94.604 percent and 96.57 percent, respectively. The values of energy evaluated by already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruitfly+SMA+CNN are 0.547 and 0.740, respectively, when there is only one round. The values of energy computed by the already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the presented Fruitfly+SMA+CNN for 2000 rounds were 0.137 and 0.15, respectively. The study according to accuracy, energy and throughput parameters is shown in Figure 5 (a) (b) and (c) respectively. When there is only one round, the current and proposed Fruitfly+SMA+CNN achieves maximum throughput with 1 and then decreases. The values of throughput measured by HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruit Fly+SMA+CNN when the number of rounds is 2000 are 0.058 and 0.063, respectively.

Figure 5. On the basis of (a) accuracy; (b) energy; and (c) throughput, a comparative analysis according to a Cleveland database using 50 nodes and 100 nodes was executed.

ii. Switzerland Database Analysis:

For a total node of 50: In terms of precision, energy, and output, a comparison of the existing HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN with the planned FRUIT FLY+SMA-CNN for 50 nodes is shown. Initially, the HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruitfly+SMA-CNN accuracy values were 85.505 % and 90.252 %, respectively. The accuracy parameters assessed by already occurring HSC-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested FRUITFLY+SMA-CNN after the method is 93.892 % and 94.209 %, respectively. The values of energy measured by already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruitfly+SMA-CNN when the number of rounds is 1 are 0.550 and 0.548, respectively. The values of energy obtained by the already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the suggested fruitfly+SMA-CNN for 2000 rounds are 0.033 and 0.076, respectively. The study based on precision, energy, and output parameters is shown in

Figure 6 (a) (b) and (c) respectively. The values of throughput measured by already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruitfly+SMA-CNN when the number of rounds is 2000 are 0.055 and 0.059, respectively.

For 100 nodes: Using 100 nodes, the present HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the proposed Fruitfly +SMA+CNN have accuracy values of 94.604 % and 97.53 %, respectively. The values of energy determined by HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested Fruitfly+SMA+CNN are 0.549 and 0.729, respectively, whenever the quantity of iterations is one. The values of energy calculated by HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested by Fruitfly+SMA+CNN for 2000 rounds are 0.111 and 0.120, respectively. The values of throughput calculated by HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and suggested FRUITFLY+SMA-CNN are 0.058 and 0.062, respectively, whenever the quantity of iterations is 2000. The study based on accuracy, energy and throughput parameters is pictured in Graph below as figure 6 (a) (b) and (c) respectively.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. Based on (a) accuracy; (b) energy; and (c) throughput, a comparative analysis according to a Switzerland database using 50 nodes and 100 nodes was executed.

Table 1. Performance Comparison of Cleveland and Switzerland Database

Dataset	Performance	HAS-PSO + FCSSA	Proposed Fruitfly+SMA
Cleveland	Accuracy	94.6%	96.57%
	Energy	0.137	0.15
	Throughput	0.058	0.063
Switzerland	Accuracy	94.6%	97.53
	Energy	0.111	0.120
	Throughput	0.058	0.062

5.6. Discussion

According to the analysis, the proposed system's performance is fruitfly+SMA. Cluster head, optimization, and classification are the strategies applied in this case. The process is carried out using the patient's medical record. The patient record is transferred to the cluster head and then moved as data. The Fruit Fly method is then used to relocate these data for optimization. It is then forwarded to the CNN classification procedure after optimization. Finally, the patient's information is evaluated. For the analysis of existing and prospective systems, we employ 50 nodes. According to the table, the existing system HSA-PSO+FCSSA can achieve power of 0.137, output of 0.058, and precision of 94.6041 percent for the Cleveland and Energy datasets, accuracy was 94.6041 percent, throughput was 0.058, and throughput was 0.111. For Cleveland datasets, the suggested system fruitfly+SMA can achieve highest performance with energy of 0.15, throughput of 0.063, and precision of 96.57 percent, and for Switzerland datasets, with energy of 0.120, throughput of 0.062, and accuracy of 97.53 percent, respectively. The values of accuracy measured by the already occurring HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN were initially 88.353 percent. The accuracy value after the process is 93.323 percent. Initially, the proposed fruitfly+SMA-CNN measured accuracy values of 90.252 percent. The accuracy value after the process is 94.206 percent. The fruitfly optimization method is preferred to the HAS-PSO optimization approach. The conventional FCSSA-DBN classification system may be slow, however the new SMA-CNN classification system is quick. Finally, a comparison is drawn between the existing HSA-PSO+FCSSA-DBN and the proposed Fruitfly+SMA-CNN. The proposed Fruitfly+SMA algorithm has the best performance, according to this investigation. As a result, it's worth noting that the proposed Fruitfly+SMA method exceeds existing approaches in terms of performance. Performance Comparison of Cleveland and Switzerland Database given in Table 1.

6. CONCLUSION

For studying health concerns and enhancing event classification accuracy for homogeneous multi-sensor networks, this research offers the Fruit Fly Algorithm and Slime Mould Algorithm (SMA) to CNN classifiers. The WBSN nodes are initially used to collect information gleaned from medical records in order to obtain a set of parameters for the evaluation. WBSN nodes deliver data to the node that drains according to the parameters acquired. The Fruit Fly Algorithm was integrated with a wireless sensor network to determine the ideal cluster head in this case. The optimization of network coverage was carried out using a novel algorithm. The Fruit Fly Algorithm's output is then sent to the node that drains, where the SMA-CNN is used to classify medical records used to assess risk and its efficiency is compared to current metaheuristics using a large collection of benchmarks. The performance comparison of 2 databases is shown in the following Table 1. For the Cleveland database, the suggested fruit fly algorithm, the method can solve peak efficiency of vitality of 0.15, throughput of 0.058, and accuracy of 96.57 and for Switzerland database, the highest performance is 0.120, throughput of 0.062, and accuracy of 97.53.

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